

ACRIDINE DERIVATIVES AS ANTIMALARIALS. PART II

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In order to study the influence of a nuclear sulphonamide-(SO₂NH₂) substituent on the chemotherapeutic properties of 5-(dialkylaminoalkyl) aminoacridine derivatives, several sulphonamide acridines have been prepared and described. The yield of condensation product from a 5-chloroacridine derivative and an amine or any amino derivative, increases with the presence of a 2-negative substituent in the former compound. The properties of the resulting condensation products indicate that they exist in acridonimine form.

The 5-aminoacridines, and more particularly those with basic substituents in the amino group, are of therapeutic interest, as their derivatives which contain a nitro or amino group possess good antiseptic properties (*cf.* Schnitzer and Silberstein, *Z. Hyg. Infek.*, 1929, **109**, 519; Albert *et al*, *Brit. J. Expt. Path.*, 1938, **19**, 41). Those which are substituted by halogen atom in any particular position show antimalarial properties (Mauss and Meitzsch, *Klin. Woch.*, 1933, **12**, 1276; Magidson and Grigorowsky, *Ber.*, 1936, **69**, 396). As compounds with a sulphonamide grouping substituted in an aromatic amine show bacteriostatic and bactericidal action against various types of cocci, it seemed of interest to undertake the preparation of 5-(dialkylaminoalkyl) aminoacridine derivatives containing a sulphonamide grouping in the acridine nucleus. The acridine derivatives that have so far been successfully used whether as an antiseptic or as an antimalarial, contain a 2-(NH₂ in case of 'Rivanol' and Cl in case of 'Atebrin') and a 7-(ethoxy in the former and methoxy in the latter) substituent. Eisleb (*Med. u. Chem.*, 1936, **3**, 41) has further observed that 2-nitro-9-aminoacridine derivatives are also good antiseptics. Again Magidson and Grigorowsky (*loc. cit.*) have noticed that the antimalarial characteristic (as judged from the chemotherapeutic index) of a 2-nitro derivative is considerably increased if the nitro group is transferred from 2-to 3-position in the molecule. A similar shifting of the chlorine atom in 2-chloro-5 (ω -diethylaminoisoamyl)-amino-7-methoxyacridine, on the contrary, practically destroys the pharmacological characteristic of the well-known drug 'Atebrin' (*cf.* Feldman and Kopeliovich, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1935, **273**, 488). Several 2- as well as 3-sulphonamido-5-(diethylaminoalkyl) amino-7-methoxyacridine derivatives have been prepared and described in the experimental part of this paper. Their

physiological properties are being studied and would be described elsewhere.

It has been noticed that the reaction of an amine with 5-chloroacridine is much facilitated and the yield of the condensation product considerably increased if the 5-chloro acridinemolecule contains a 2-negative substituent. Such an enhanced mobility of the 5-chlorine atom has also been noticed by Eisleb (*loc. cit.*). The stability of the condensation product again seems to be dependent on the substituent at the 5-amino-nitrogen (*cf.* Choudhury, Das-Gupta and Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 735; Magidson and Grigorowsky, *loc. cit.* Drozdov, *J. Gen. Chem.*, 1936, **6**, 1641). These 5-aminoacridine derivatives are deeper in colour than their dihydrochloride salts. The latter again are readily precipitated from their aqueous solution by traces of sodium chloride. The alcoholic solutions of the bases are also more fluorescent than those of their salts. All these point to the fact that most probably these acridine derivatives or better their salts exist preferably in an isomeric acridonimine form as has been suggested by

Goodal and Kermack (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1547), who observed the non-reactivity of 5-chloro-compound with a secondary amine (*cf.* Drozdov, *loc. cit.*). 2-Chloro-5-amino-7-methoxy acridine (I) has been found to possess all the usual characteristics of a 5-aminoacridine derivative. The compound gives no diazoreaction (*cf.* Albert and Linnel, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1615 who found 2-chloro-5-aminoacridine to be not readily diazotisable). Albert and Linnel (*loc. cit.*) suggested the acridonimine formula for the amine.

o-Chlorobenzoic acid did not react with *p*-aminobenzene-sulphonamide under the usual conditions. 2:4-Dichlorobenzoic acid, however, gave a diphenylamine derivative (II) as usual but acridination of (II) was unsuccessful. The synthesis of 2-chloro-7-aminoacridine derivatives is in progress and it may be mentioned here that 2:5-dichloro-7-acetylaminoacridine, obtained by reacting 2:4-dichloro-benzoic acid with *p*-aminoacetanilide and by subsequent acridination, hydrolyses to 2-chloro-7-aminoacridone. The latter underwent diazotization as expected

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

2-Sulphonamido-7-methoxy-5-dialkylaminoalkylamino-acridines.

2-Chloro-4-sulphonamido-benzoic Acid.—2-Chloro-4-sulphonamidotoluene was prepared by reacting *o*-chlorotoluene and chlorosulphonic acid (1 : 5) at a low temperature and finishing the reaction by heating the mixture at 60° for 2 hours. The resulting mixture was poured over ice and the semi-solid mass was directly treated with liquor ammonia, when a crystalline product was obtained, which was recrystallised from benzene, m. p. 121-23°. (Found : N, 7·06. $C_7H_8O_2NCIS$ requires N, 6·81 per cent). 2-Chloro-3-sulphonamidotoluene has m. p. 128° (*cf.* Wynne, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1892, 61, 1036).

The sulphonamidotoluene (1 mol.) was refluxed with a 10% solution of potassium permanganate (2·2 mol.) till the colour of permanganate was discharged. After the removal of manganese dioxide the filtrate was acidified with hydrochloric acid and evaporated to a small volume and allowed to cool. 2-Chloro-4-sulphonamidobenzoic acid crystallised out in fine needles, m.p. 198-99°. (Found : N, 6·04. $C_7H_6O_4NCIS$ requires N, 5·94 per cent).

5-Sulphonamido-4'-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic Acid.—A mixture of 2-chloro-4-sulphonamidobenzoic acid (2·3 g.), *p*-anisidine (1·2 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (1·4 g.), copper powder (0·1 g.) and amyl alcohol (25 c. c.) was refluxed together for about 5 hours. Most of the amyl alcohol was removed by distillation and the residual mass after dilution with water was steam-distilled to remove the last traces of amyl alcohol and anisidine. It was then filtered hot (charcoal), cooled and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The diphenylamine-carboxylic acid, thus isolated, was crystallised from dilute alcohol and obtained in greenish yellow needles, m.p. 242°. (Found : N, 8·62. $C_{14}H_{14}O_5N_2S$ requires N, 8·7 per cent).

2-Sulphonamido-5-chloro-7-methoxyacridine.—The above diphenylamine-carboxylic acid was heated with excess of phosphorus oxychloride on a boiling water-bath for 2 hours. The excess of phosphorus oxychloride was removed *in vacuo*. The residual mass was treated with ice-cold water and made alkaline with ammonia. The crude chloroacridine, thus obtained, was crystallised from acetone in small yellow needles, decomposing slowly above 240°, yield theoretical. (Found : N, 8·48. $C_{14}H_{11}O_3N_2ClS$ requires N, 8·68 per cent). The compound is soluble in both acids and alkalis. It gives feeble fluorescence in dilute alcoholic solution.

2-Sulphonamido-7-methoxy-5-(ω -diethylamino-isoamyl)-aminoacridine.—The above chloroacridine (1 g.) was dissolved in phenol and heated with

δ -diethylamino- α -methylbutylamine (0.7 g.) for about 1 hour. The reaction mixture was poured into sodium hydroxide solution. On stirring a clear solution was obtained. This was extracted with ether several times and made faintly alkaline by adding dilute hydrochloric acid. A viscous mass separated, which solidified on washing with cold water. It was dissolved in dilute acetic acid, the acid solution was filtered, extracted with ether and made alkaline with ammonia. The base, thus obtained, was collected and dried. It crystallised from acetone-petroleum ether mixture (1 : 4) in orange-yellow crystals, m.p. 115-120°. (Found: N, 12.10; S, 7.52. $C_{22}H_{32}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 12.61; S, 7.21 per cent). The substance is extremely bitter in taste and is highly soluble in alcohol, acids and dilute alkalis. Its alcoholic solution exhibits emerald-green fluorescence. In acids the fluorescence is weaker.

2-Sulphonamido - 7-methoxy - 5 - (δ -diethylaminobutyl)aminoacridine.—2-Sulphonamido-5-chloro-7-methoxyacridine (1 g.) dissolved in phenol was heated with δ -diethylaminobutylamine (0.6 g.). The reaction mixture was subsequently treated as in the previous case and the base was finally crystallised from acetone-petroleum ether (1 : 3) mixture in yellow microscopic needles, m.p. 110-115°. (Found: N, 12.82. $C_{22}H_{30}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 13.02 per cent. It is also highly soluble in alcohol and difficultly soluble in ether. It resembles the previous compound in the fluorescence of its alcoholic and acid solutions.

3-Sulphonamido-7-methoxy-5-dialkylaminoalkyl-aminoacridines.

2-Chloro-5-sulphonamidobenzoic Acid.—*o*-Chlorobenzoic acid (1 mol.) was slowly added to chloro sulphonic acid (5 mol.) cooled in ice. The mixture was gradually heated up to 90-95° and kept at that temperature for 1½-2 hours. It was finally poured into crushed ice with stirring when the sulphonyl chloride derivative (m.p. 101° on crystallisation from petroleum ether) separated. It was dissolved in strong ammonia and the solution on acidification gave 2-chloro-5-sulphonamidobenzoic acid which crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 217-19°. (Found: N, 6.12. $C_7H_6O_4NCIS$ requires N, 5.94 per cent).

2-Chloro-5-sulphondiethylamidobenzoic Acid.—The sulphonyl chloride, obtained in the previous experiment, when treated with diethylamine and the resulting solution acidified gave the acid in colourless needles, m.p. 147° after crystallisation from benzene. (Found: N, 4.91. $C_{11}H_{14}O_4NCIS$ requires N, 4.8 per cent).

2-Chloro-5-sulphonphenylamidobenzoic Acid.—The sulphonyl chloride with aniline gave after isolation in the usual manner 2-chloro-5-sulphon-

phenylamidobenzoic acid, m.p. 194-95° after crystallisation from dilute alcohol in colourless needles. (Found : N, 4'67. $C_{13}H_{10}O_4NClS$ requires N, 4'49 per cent).

4-Sulphonamido-4'-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic Acid.—2-Chloro-5-sulphonamidobenzoic acid (2'3 g.), *p*-anisidine (1'2 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (1'4 g.) and copper powder (0'1 g.) were refluxed in amyl alcohol for several hours. After treatment of the reaction product in the way as described under 5-sulphonamido-4'-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid, the crude product was isolated as a semi-solid mass. This was finally crystallised from dilute alcohol (charcoal) in greenish yellow needles, m.p. 239-40°. (Found : N, 8'53. $C_{14}H_{14}O_5N_2S$ requires N, 8'7 per cent).

4-Sulphondiethylamido-4'-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic Acid.—2-Chloro-5-sulphondiethylamidobenzoic acid, when reacted with *p*-anisidine under the above conditions, afforded the related diphenylamine-carboxylic acid, m.p. 170-71° after crystallisation from dilute alcohol. (Found : N, 7'51. $C_{18}H_{22}O_5N_2S$ requires N, 7'4 per cent).

4-Sulphonphenylamido-4'-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic Acid.—2-Chloro-5-sulphonphenylamidobenzoic acid, when treated with *p*-anisidine under the usual conditions, afforded the diphenylamine derivative which after crystallisation from rectified spirit (charcoal) in fine yellow needles had m.p. 233°. (Found : N, 7'22. $C_{20}H_{18}O_5N_2S$ requires N, 7'04 per cent).

3-Sulphonamido-5-chloro-7-methoxyacridine.—4-Sulphonamido-4'-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid was heated with excess of phosphorus oxychloride and the reaction mixture was subsequently treated in the way as described in the preparation of 2-sulphonamido-5-chloro-7-methoxyacridine. The product crystallised from acetone in yellow needles decomposing slowly above 230°. (Found : Cl, 10'95. $C_{14}H_{11}O_3N_2ClS$ requires Cl, 11'01 per cent). The yield is about 80-90 % of the theory. It is soluble in dilute acids and alkalis.

3-Sulphondiethylamido-5-chloro-7-methoxyacridine.—4-Sulphondiethylamido-4'-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid when reacted with phosphorus oxychloride afforded the above acridine derivative. It crystallises from benzene (charcoal) in yellow microscopic needles, m.p. 184-86°. (Found : N, 7'51. $C_{18}H_{19}O_3N_2ClS$ requires N, 7'39 per cent). It is soluble in dilute acids but insoluble in dilute alkalis. The compound is fluorescent in solution.

3-Sulphonphenylamido-5-chloro-7-methoxyacridine was also prepared in the same way by treating 4-sulphonphenylamido-4'-methoxydiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid with phosphorus oxychloride. It separates from

acetone as yellow needles, m.p. 207-208°. (Found : N, 7.06. $C_{20}H_{15}O_3N_2ClS$ requires N, 7.02 per cent). It is again soluble both in acids and alkalis.

3-Sulphonamido-7-methoxy-5-(ω -diethylamino-isoamyl)aminoacridine.—3-Sulphonamido-5-chloro-7-methoxyacridine on treatment with δ -diethylamino- α -methylbutylamine as previously described in the case of 2-sulphonamido compound, afforded the above sulphonamidoacridine. It crystallised from a mixture of acetone and petroleum ether in the cold in yellow needles, m.p. indefinite, ca 135°. (Found : N, 12.29. $C_{23}H_{32}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 12.61 per cent). It is soluble in dilute acids and alkalis, slightly soluble in ether but freely in alcohol. The hydrochloride has less intense fluorescence than the free base.

3-Sulphonamido-7-methoxy-5-(δ -diethylaminobutyl) aminoacridine.—The foregoing chloroacridine derivative on treatment with δ -diethylaminobutylamine gave the 5-aminoacridine derivative which separated from acetone-petroleum ether mixture in orange-yellow needles, melting indefinitely at 138°. (Found : N, 12.76 ; S 7.71. $C_{22}H_{30}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 13.02 ; S 7.44 per cent). It is bitter in taste and possesses all the usual characteristics of the 5-aminoacridine derivatives.

3-Sulphondiethylamido-7-methoxy-5-(ω -diethylaminoisoamyl) aminoacridine.—The corresponding 5-chloro derivative with the δ -diethylamino- α -methylbutylamine gave this amino derivative as a low melting solid. Accordingly this was extracted with ether, ethereal solution dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate, and treated with dry hydrogen chloride. The dihydrochloride, thus obtained, was collected and crystallised from alcohol-ether mixture (1 : 2) as a yellow crystalline powder, m.p. 240-41°. (Found : N, 9.66 ; Cl, 12.12. $C_{27}H_{40}O_3N_4S$, 2 HCl requires N, 9.77 ; Cl, 12.39 per cent). The *dihydrochloride* is extremely soluble in water and alcohol and bitter in taste. The base is more coloured than this hydrochloride, the latter being less fluorescent in solution than the former.

3-Sulphondiethylamido-7-methoxy-5-(δ -diethylaminobutyl) aminoacridine.—3-Sulphondiethylamino-5-chloroacridine derivative with δ -diethylaminobutylamine also afforded the base as usual. The product was converted into the dihydrochloride as in the former case, which was finally crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and ether in canary yellow needles, m.p. 251-52°. (Found : N, 9.97 ; Cl, 12.59. $C_{26}H_{38}O_3N_4S$, 2HCl requires N, 10.02 ; Cl, 12.7 per cent). In this case also the base is more coloured and imparts more fluorescence to its alcoholic solution. This base is highly soluble in ether as well as in alcohol.

3-Sulphonphenylamido-7-methoxy-5-(ω -diethylaminoisoamyl) aminoacridine.—The compound was obtained from the corresponding 5-chloro

acridine derivative and the appropriate amine. It separates from acetone-petroleum ether mixture in orange-yellow crystals, melting indefinitely at 105-110°. (Found : N, 10.59. $C_{29}H_{36}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 10.77 per cent).

3-Sulphophenylamido-7-methoxy-5-(ω-diethylaminobutyl) aminoacridine.—It was isolated in the usual manner and found to separate from acetone-petroleum ether in orange-yellow needles melting indefinitely at 100°-105°. (Found : N, 10.87 ; S, 6.7. $C_{28}H_{34}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 11.07 ; S, 6.32 per cent). The compound is soluble in acids, alkalis, alcohol and ether, and is highly fluorescent in solution.

5-Chloro-4'-sulphonamidodiphenylamine-4-carboxylic Acid.—Equimolecular quantities of 2 : 4-dichlorobenzoic acid and *p*-aminobenzenesulphonamide under the usual conditions afforded the foregoing substance. Crystallised from dilute alcohol (charcoal) in greenish-yellow needles it had m.p. 207°. (Found : N 8.29. $C_{13}H_{11}O_4N_2ClS$ requires N, 8.57 per cent). The compound was heated with phosphorus oxychloride, and with a mixture of the latter and phosphorus pentachloride at various temperatures up to 150°, but no acridination took place. Similarly 2 : 4-dichlorobenzoic acid and *p*-aminobenzenesulphonamide gave 5-chloro-4'-sulphondiethylamidodiphenylamine-4-carboxylic acid, m.p. 101-102°. (Found : N 7.07 ; Cl, 9.41. $C_{17}H_{13}O_4N_2ClS$ requires N, 7.47 ; Cl, 9.48 per cent). The acid also resisted acridination.

5-Chloro-4'-acetylaminodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic Acid.—The 2:4-dichlorobenzoic acid and *p*-aminoacetanilide in molecular proportions under the usual conditions afforded the related diphenylamine-carboxylic acid, m.p. 287-88°, after crystallisation from a large volume of alcohol. (Found : N, 8.96. $C_{15}H_{13}O_3N_2Cl$ requires N, 9.19 per cent).

2 : 5-Dichloro-7-acetylaminoadine.—The above compound on treatment with phosphorus oxychloride afforded the chloroacridine in fine orange needles, m.p. 242-43° after crystallisation from benzene. (Found : N 8.91. $C_{15}H_{10}ON_2Cl_2$ requires N, 9.18 per cent).

2-Chloro-7-aminoacridone.—The foregoing chloroacridine (0.5 g.) was boiled with 15 c.c. of hydrochloric acid (24 %) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The reaction mixture was diluted with water, cooled and the solid was triturated with ammonia and filtered. The aminoacridone was crystallised from alcohol in dark red needles, decomposing above 250°. (Found : Cl, 14.3. $C_{13}H_9ON_2Cl$ requires Cl, 14.51 per cent). It is sparingly soluble in ether and benzene, but is soluble in acids and gives a diazo reaction.